

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Numonova Shakhrizoda

**IMODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE AT
MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES**

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